

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SERVICE SECTOR IN THE IMPROVEMENT OF THE COUNTRY

Abror Rashidov Ruzimurod ugli¹

Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan

KEYWORDS

GDP, PQ-104, PQ-5113, the
volume of services has grown

ABSTRACT

The reason for the development of the service sector is to ensure employment by creating new jobs, as well as a sphere with great potential in the development of the country. The real increase in incomes of the population in places can also be clearly seen, first of all, from the development of services. In this regard, we will focus on the development of the services sector and strengthening its role in the structure of the economy. This area is able not only to provide jobs in rural areas, as well as increase the income of the population, while remaining in urban areas.

2181-2675/© 2022 in XALQARO TADQIQOT LLC.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7372535

This is an open access article under the Attribution 4.0 International(CC BY 4.0) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.ru>)

¹ Assistant, Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan, Jizzakh, Uzbekistan

The service sector is one of the largest reserves in ensuring employment of the population. In our country, its share in the gross domestic product (GDP) is 36.3%, and the number of people employed in the industry is 50.1%. Considering that now there are great opportunities for creating jobs in this area in our republic, this is still a very low indicator.

In order to develop this sphere, decisions, various measures and projects are being developed by the head of our country. In particular, in the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 11.05.2021 PQ-5113, in order to increase the share of the services sector in the economy of our country, to fully launch existing opportunities in the field of services on the ground, to solve problematic issues awaiting their solution to expand the range of services:

In 2021-2023, the main areas of development of the services sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan were defined as:

- ▶ making the services sector an important driver in ensuring economic growth and doubling the volume of services by 2023;

- ▶ to provide the population with ready-made business plans and projects, to organize the provision of "complex services" covering the stages from training them in the profession to the establishment of entrepreneurial activity;

- ▶ increase the efficiency of the activities of state bodies and organizations in this regard and strengthen the responsibility of officials by introducing a system for assessing the development of the services sector in the Republic;

- ▶ elimination of excessive bureaucratic barriers in the field of services, expansion of the range of services based on the specifics of each area, expansion of the coverage of transport, financial, as well as banking, tourism and trade services in the regions, especially in rural areas;

- ▶ to increase the potential of existing educational and health services in all regions of the Republic, to improve their quality, to create favorable economic and infrastructural conditions for attracting the private sector[1], the resolution of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 27.01.2022 PQ-104[2], projects such as "New Uzbekistan" have been developed, and, it is no exaggeration to say that in our country, which is developing day by day, there will be tremendous changes.

As a result of ensuring the implementation of Resolution No. 5113 PQ, the volume of services in 2021 increased by almost 20%.

At the same time, by introducing new approaches to the development of the services sector, there will be opportunities to increase the volume of market services by 1.5 times this year and create an additional 1.5 million new jobs.

REFERENCE:

1. PQ-5113-сoн 11.05.2021. Xizmatlar sohasini jadal rivojlantirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida (lex.uz)

2. PQ-104-сoн 27.01.2022. Xizmatlar sohasini rivojlantirishga oid qo'shimcha chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida (lex.uz)

3. Akramovich N. A. THE PRIORITY OF USING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE AGRICULTURAL EDUCATION SYSTEM //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 10. – С. 185-191.
4. Nizametdinov A., Ahmedova H. Elektron ta'lim metodologiyasi rivojlantirishning usullari //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollar. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 29-31.
5. Nizametdinov A. A. OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMINING AGRAR SOHASIDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR QO'LLASH USTUVORLIGI. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES, 1 (6), 58-60. – 2022.
6. Nizametdinov A. A. OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMIDA AGRAR SOHANING USTUVORLIGI UNDA INNOVATSIYALARNING QULLANISHI. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES, 1 (6), 96-98. – 2022.
7. Akramovich N. A. HISTORY, SUBJECT AND OBJECT OF FORMATION OF" MACROECONOMICS" //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 10. – №. 1. – С. 209-210.
8. Мухтаров Б. А. Оптимальное распределение объемов строительно-монтажных работ //Молодой ученый. – 2018. – №. 22. – С. 427-431.
9. Мухтаров Б. А. Имитационная система прогнозирования факторов в легкой промышленности //Молодой ученый. – 2017. – №. 40. – С. 122-124.
10. Мухтаров Б. А., Ортиков Ё. Ю. Культурное и экономическое развитие туризма в Узбекистане //Молодой ученый. – 2016. – №. 14. – С. 375-378.
11. Muxtarov B., Murotjonova M. O'zbekiston respublikasida kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlik sub 'ektlarining rivojlanishi //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollar. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 581-584.
12. Muxtarov B. Ozbekiston respublikasida axoli daromadlarini osish dinamikasi //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollar. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 579-581.
13. Мухтаров Б. А., Джамалов У. И. ПРОГНОЗИРОВАНИЕ КОЛИЧЕСТВО ШКОЛ НА 2022 ГОД ДЛЯ РОССИЙСКОЙ ФЕДЕРАЦИИ //Устойчивое развитие науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 8. – С. 6-11.
14. Abdusattarovich M. B. CALCULATING ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 1189-1194.
15. Ogli R. A. R. THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN THE CONCEPTS OF DATABASE AND DATABASE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM //Archive of Conferences. – 2022. – С. 33-34.
16. Abdukarimov A., Rashidov A. Ma'lumotlar bazalarining–biznesni tashil etish va samaradorligini oshirishdagi roli //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollar. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 132-135.

17. Uchkun Rashidov, Abror Rashidov, & Saidjon Naimov. (2022). Modern Views on the Problems of Management Accounting in Logistics System. "ONLINE - CONFERENCES" PLATFORM, 276–283. Retrieved from <http://papers.online-conferences.com/index.php/titfl/article/view/937>
18. Uchkun Rashidov, & Abror Rashidov. (2022). Assessment of Costs For the Quality of Logistics Activities. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS DIPLOMACY AND ECONOMY, 1(3), 39–43. Retrieved from <http://inter-publishing.com/index.php/ijbde/article/view/128>
19. Uchkun Rashidov, & Abror Rashidov. (2022). Assessment of Costs For the Quality of Logistics Activities. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS DIPLOMACY AND ECONOMY, 1(3), 39–43. Retrieved from <http://inter-publishing.com/index.php/ijbde/article/view/128>
20. Dots. Abdumanap Abdukarimov, & Assist. Abror Rashidov R. (2022). 7 FREE BEST OPEN SOURCE DATABASE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS. Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development, 7, 40–47. Retrieved from <https://sjird.journalspark.org/index.php/sjird/article/view/234>
21. Rashidov , A. (2022). IQTISODIYOTNI TARTIBGA SOLISHDA NOTARIF USULLARINING O`RNI VA AHAMIYATI. Архив научных исследований, 2(1). извлечено от <http://journal.tsue.uz/index.php/archive/article/view/1016>
22. Rashidov Abror Ro'zimurod o'g'li. (2022). JIZZAX VILOYATI IQTISODIY O'SISH KO'RSATKICHLARI YOKI JARAYONLARI . PEDAGOGS Jurnal, 5(1), 20–22. Retrieved from <http://www.pedagoglar.uz/index.php/ped/article/view/290>
23. Рашидов У., Рашидов А. Iqtisodiyotni tartibga solishda notarif usullarining ornı va ahamiyati //Вопросы усиления позиций Узбекистана в международной торговле и оптимизации его интеграции в мировой рынок в условиях глобальной трансформации. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 53-58.
24. Ismailova N. S. et al. JAHON SAVDO TASHKILOTIGA QO'SHILISH: QO'SHILISH JARAYONI HAMDA UNING QONUNIY ASOSLARI //Scientific progress. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 1095-1098.
25. Xaydarov, B., & Saitov, S. (2022). Raqamli iqtisodiyot tushunchasi va afzalliklari. Zamonaviy Innovatsion Tadqiqotlarning Dolzarb Muammolari Va Rivojlanish Tendensiyalari: Yechimlar Va Istiqbollar, 1(1), 634–635. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/zitdmrt/article/view/5390>
26. Бахром Х. Х. БИЗНЕСНИ РЕЖАЛАШТИРИШ ТАРТИБЛАРИ //PEDAGOGS jurnal. – 2022. – Т. 12. – №. 2. – С. 139-142.
27. Xaydarov B. X., Saitov S. A. RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT TUSHUNCHASI, AFZALLIKLARI AMALIY AHAMIYATI VA XORIJIY TAJRIBA //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 151-156.

28. Хайдаров Б. ИҚТИСОДИЙ ИСЛОҲОТЛАРНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА КАМБАҒАЛЛИКНИ ҚИСҚАРТИРИШ //Экономика и образование. – 2021. – №. 4. – С. 288-292.
29. То'uchiyeva N. Elektron Ta 'lim Tizimining Afzalliklari Va Kamchiliklari //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollor. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 40-41.
30. Норбеков Х., Туйчиева Н. Формирование конкурентных преимуществ компании //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollor. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 589-592.
31. Nodira T., Maxfirat T. FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF PRONUNCIATION IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING IN SCHOOL STUDENTS //INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES ON LEARNING AND TEACHING. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1.
32. Nodira T., Maxfirat T. MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE PRONUNCIATION TO PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS IS BASED ON THE JAPANESE EXPERIENCE //ТА'ЛИМ ВА РИВОЖЛАНИШ ТАҲЛИЛИ ОНЛАЙН ИЛМИЙ ЖУРНАЛИ. – 2022. – С. 205-208.
33. Nodira T., Rashid X. PROBLEMS OF INNOVATION MANAGEMENT IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 155-164.
34. Nodira T. PRIORITIES FOR ORGANIZING ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITIES IN THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 10. – С. 192-199.
35. Nodira T. INNOVATIVE MANAGEMENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 10. – С. 346-351.
36. То'uchiyeva, N. (2022). AGRAR SOHADA TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINI TASHKIL ETISHGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES, 1(4), 53–56. Retrieved from <http://researchedu.org/index.php/cf/article/view/625>
37. То'uchiyeva , N. (2022). AGRAR TARMOQDA TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINI TASHKIL ETISHNING TASHKILY-IQTISODIY ASOSLARI. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES, 1(4), 3–6. Retrieved from <http://researchedu.org/index.php/cf/article/view/624>
38. То'uchiyeva N. THE MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF INNOVATION MANAGEMENT IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM //INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 103-105.
39. Nodira T., Maxfirat T. FOREIGN LANGUAGE PRONUNCIATION IN GRADES 1-4» //РЕДАКЦИОННАЯ КОЛЛЕГИЯ. – С. 1133.
40. Хосилмуродов И. О 'zbekistonda bag 'rikenglik va millatlararo totuvlik g 'oyalarining ijtimoiy hayotdagi ahamiyati //Общество и инновации. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 11/S. – С. 16-24.

41. Ҳосилмуродов И., Султоналиева Г. Тафаккур услубининг фалсафий-методологик таҳлили //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollar. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 549-551.
42. Арзикулов О. А. Значение малого бизнеса и частного предпринимательства в узбекистана //Экономика и социум. – 2020. – №. 4. – С. 157-160.
43. Maksimov Y. V. et al. The integrating role of systems engineer in oil and gas projects (Russian) //Neftyanoe khozyaystvo-Oil Industry. – 2019. – Т. 2019. – №. 12. – С. 12-15.
44. Arzikulov O. A. THE ROLE OF SMALL BUSINESS IN DEVELOPED COUNTRIES //Экономика и социум. – 2019. – №. 12. – С. 30-33.
45. Arzikulov O. UY XO'JALIKLARINING DAROMAD MANBALARI VA ISTE'MOL XARAJATLARINI STATISTIK KO'RSATKICHLARINI O'RGANISH //Архив Научных Публикаций JSPI. – 2020.
46. Ali o'g'li A. O. STATISTICAL STUDY OF DIRECT MAINTENANCE OF SMALL BUSINESS ACTIVITIES IN THE REGIONS //EPRA International Journal of Economic and Business Review (JEER). – 2022. – Т. 10. – №. 6. – С. 30-33.
47. Arzikulov O. Iqtisodiyotni liberallashtirish sharoitida kichik korxonalarda innovatsion jarayonlar //Архив Научных Публикаций JSPI. – 2020.
48. To'ychiyeva, Nodira. "Elektron Ta'lim Tizimining Afzalliklari Va Kamchiliklari." Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollar 1.1 (2022): 40-41.
49. Норбеков, Хурсандмурод, and Нодира Туйчиева. "Формирование конкурентных преимуществ компании." Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollar 1.1 (2022): 589-592.
50. Jamshidovna B. M., Bahodirovich F. S. Innovative methods and techniques in the education system //current research journal of pedagogics. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 11. – С. 147-151.
51. Fayzullaev S. B. Fostering the qualities of agility of basketball pupils in Uzbekistan //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 5. – С. 1171-1176.
52. Fayzullaeva D. N. et al. Dialectisms used in dastan "Alpamish" //ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 12 (80). – 2019. – С. 469-472.
53. Nasirov B. U., Boltaeva M. J. Genesis And Transformation Of The Public Catering System In Uzbekistan During The Soviet Period //Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry (TOJQI) Volume. – Т. 12. – С. 5834-5841.
54. Nasirov B. Catering In Uzbekistan From The History Of The System //The American Journal of Interdisciplinary Innovations Research. – 2021. – Т. 3. – №. 02. – С. 11-15.

55. Насиров Б. ХХ АСРНИНГ 30-80 ЙИЛЛАРИДА ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА УМУМИЙ ОВҚАТЛАНИШ ТИЗИМИ ТАРИХИДАН //ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ. – 2022. – Т. 5. – №. 1.
56. Носиров Б., Носирова Ф. Ўзбекистонда умумий овқатланиш тизимининг шаклланиши ва унга аҳоли эҳтиёжининг ортиб бориши (совет ҳукумати йилларида) //ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ. – 2020. – Т. 3. – №. 3.
57. Носиров Б. Совет даврида Ўзбекистонда умумий овқатланиш тизими фаолияти хусусида //Взгляд в прошлое. – 2021. – Т. 4. – №. 4.
58. Насыров Б. У. История деятельности бань в восточных странах //International scientific review. – 2016. – №. 4 (14). – С. 62-66.
59. Носиров Б., Носирова Ф. СИСТЕМА БЫТОВОГО ОБСЛУЖИВАНИЯ: ГЕНЕЗИС И ПРОБЛЕМЫ ПРАКТИКИ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ РЕСПУБЛИКИ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН В 60-80 ГОДЫ ПРОШЛОГО ВЕКА) //Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире. – 2017. – №. 1-4. – С. 41-46.
60. Nasirov B. HISTORICAL SCIENCES //Главный редактор научно-исследовательского журнала «International scientific review», Вальцев СВ. – 2016. – №. 4. – С. 61.
61. Носиров Б. Механизмы и противоречивое развитие сферы бытового обслуживания в Узбекистане 20-40 годах ХХ века //Культура. Духовность. Общество. – 2014. – №. 11. – С. 158-163.
62. Uralovich N. B. TRANSFORMATIONAL PROCESSES IN THE GENERAL FOOD SYSTEM (in the example of the catering system in the late 19th and early 20th centuries) //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 1253-1258.
63. Носиров Б. ИЖТИМОЙ-МАИШИЙ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРАЛАРНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА ЭЪТИБОРГА ОЛИНМАГАН ОМИЛЛАР (СОВЕТ ДАВРИДА): Носиров Бунёд, Тарих фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори, доцент. Мирзо Улуғбек номидаги Ўзбекистон Миллий университети Жиззах филиали //Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал. – 2022. – №. 4. – С. 8-12.
64. Musaev O. et al. The role of public control in improving the system of public administration //Solid State Technology. – 2020. – Т. 63. – №. 6. – С. 96-104.
65. E'tiborxon Mallayeva S. M. МАФКУРА ВА МАФКУРАВИЙ КАТЕГОРИЯЛАР ЎРТАСИДАГИ ЎЗАРО МУНОСАБАТНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ ЖИ //АТЛАРИ, Архив Научных Публикаций JSPI. – 2020.
66. E'tiborxon Mallayeva M. иллик ва миллий-маънавий? адриятларнинг тикланиши //Архив Научных Публикаций JSPI. – 2020.
67. Маллаева Э. Збекистонда диний бағрикенглик ва миллатлараро муносабатлар масалалари //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollari. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 573-576.

68. Fedotova M. A., Tarasova V. N., Mallaeva E. M. Factors and Conditions of Effective Dynamic Innovative Development of Aviation Industry Enterprises //Proceedings of the International Conference Engineering Innovations and Sustainable Development. – Springer, Cham, 2022. – С. 309-318.
69. Маллаева Э. APPROACHES AND ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPT OF POLITICAL CULTURE //Herald pedagogiki. Nauka i Praktyka. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1.
70. Маллаева Э. М. ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ ПОЛИТИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ ГРАЖДАН НА ОСНОВЕ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ИДЕИ //ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ. – 2019. – С. 31-34.
71. МАЛЛАЕВА Э. М. ИСТОРИЧЕСКИЙ И НАУЧНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ КОНЦЕПЦИИ ПОЛИТИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ //Вопросы политологии. – 2019. – Т. 9. – №. 8. – С. 1722-1729.
72. Маллаева Э. Jamiyatning demokratlashuvi-fuqarolar siyosiy madaniyatini rivojlantirish omili sifatida //Общество и инновации. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 11/S. – С. 287-291.
73. Mallaeva E. Les enfants réfugiés de la révolution hongroise de 1956 en Yougoslavie: entre tensions géopolitiques et efforts de coopération humanitaire. – 2020.
74. Xaydarov B., Saitov S. Raqamli iqtisodiyot tushunchasi va afzalliklari //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollari. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 634-635.
75. Xaydarov B. X., Saitov S. A. RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT TUSHUNCHASI, AFZALLIKLARI AMALIY ANAMIYATI VA XORIJIY TAJRIBA //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 151-156.
76. Bozorboevich R. K. The Ethnic Structure of the Population of the Bukhara Emirate //International Journal on Integrated Education. – Т. 4. – №. 12. – С. 8-12.
77. Рахматов Х. Б. БУХОРО АМИРЛИГИ АҲОЛИСИНИНГ ЭТНИК ТАРКИБИ ХУСУСИДА (XIX асрнинг иккинчи ярми–XX аср бошлари) //ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ. – 2021. – №. SI-3.
78. Рахматов Х. Б. Об Этнической Структуре Населения Бухарского Эмирата //INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES. – 2021. – Т. 2. – С. 273-278.
79. Bozorboevich R. K. The Ethnic Structure of the Population of the Bukhara Emirate //International Journal on Integrated Education. – Т. 4. – №. 12. – С. 8-12.
80. Рахматов Х., Набиев Ш. XIX асрнинг сўнги чораги–XX аср бошларида бухоро воҳаси сиёсий-маъмурий бирликлари ва аҳолиси хусусида //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollari. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 605-608.
81. Bozorboevich R. K. POLITICAL AND ADMINISTRATIVE STRUCTURE OF THE EMIRATE OF BUKHARA IN THE LATE XIX AND EARLY XX CENTURIES ON THE POPULATION

AND ETHNOTOPONYMS //CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF HISTORY (2767-472X). – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 04. – С. 48-54.

82. Bozorboevich R. K. ON THE POPULATION AND ETHNIC PROCESSES OF THE POLITICAL-ADMINISTRATIVE UNITS OF THE MIDDLE BASIN OF THE AMUDARYA IN THE LAST QUARTER OF THE 19TH CENTURY AND THE BEGINNING OF THE 20TH CENTURY //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 77-85.

83. Рахматов Х. Б. БУХОРО АМИРЛИГИ АҲОЛИСИНИНГ ЭТНИК ТАРКИБИ ХУСУСИДА (XIX асрнинг иккинчи ярми–XX аср бошлари) //ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ. – 2021. – №. SI-3.

84. Xaydarov B., Saitov S. Raqamli iqtisodiyot tushunchasi va afzalliklari //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollar. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 634-635.

85. Бахром Х. Х. БИЗНЕСНИ РЕЖАЛАШТИРИШ ТАРТИБЛАРИ //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – Т. 12. – №. 2. – С. 139-142.

86. Xaydarov B. X., Saitov S. A. RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT TUSHUNCHASI, AFZALLIKLARI AMALIY ANAMIYATI VA HORIJIIY TAJRIBA //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 151-156.

87. Хайдаров Б. ИҚТИСОДИЙ ИСЛОҲОТЛАРНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА КАМБАҒАЛЛИКНИ ҚИСҚАРТИРИШ //Экономика и образование. – 2021. – №. 4. – С. 288-292.

88. G'aybullayev Sarvar O. et al. O 'ZBEKISTONDA ISTE'MOL SAVATCHASI HOZIRGI HOLATINI VA UNI SHAKILLANTIRISH YO 'NALISHLARI //Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 119-125.

89. Xudayarov R., Akhror A. BIG DATA TYPES OF EDUCATION SYSTEM AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR USING THEM IN THE FIELD //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 21-24.

90. Nodira T., Rashid X. PROBLEMS OF INNOVATION MANAGEMENT IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 155-164.

91. Khudoyarov R. IMPROVING ECONOMIC GOVERNANCE IN A MARKET ECONOMY //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 10. – №. 2. – С. 610-612.

92. Хакимов О. М., Курбанов З. Х., Мухаммедов Ф. Реализация возможностей получения легких наполнителей на основе меньше пластиковых почв в нашей республике //Science and Education. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 176-181.

93. Khakimov O. M. Issiq-quruq iqlim sharoiti uchun asfaltbeton tarkibini tanlash //Science and Education. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 241-247.

94. Хакимов О., Курбонов З. ПЛАСТИКЛИГИ КАМ ТУПРОҚЛАР АСОСИДА ЕНГИЛ ТЎЛДИРУВЧИЛАР ОЛИШ ИМКОНИАТЛАРИНИ ЎРГАНИШ //Solution of social problems in management and economy. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 58-64.
95. Azimov Y. H. et al. Olympism and olympic education at the present stage //Фундаментальные и прикладные исследования в современном мире. – 2016. – №. 13-4. – С. 119-121.
96. Azimov Yusufjon. (2022). DEVELOP CREATIVE THINKING IN STUDENTS BASED ON A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH. CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS, 3(03), 5–8. <https://doi.org/10.37547/pedagogics-crijp-03-03-02>
97. Abror Ro'zimurod o'g R. et al. O 'ZBEKISTONDA PUL-KREDIT TIZIMI VA UNI MODERNIZATSIYALASH YO 'LLARI //O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 13. – С. 251-258.
98. Khidirov K. I. et al. Military management and army structure of Sheybanids //The Fourth International conference on development of historical and political sciences in Eurasia. – 2015. – С. 8-11.
99. Ortikov O. K. et al. Views of eastern thinkers on the development of intellectual abilities in the scientific heritage //ACADEMICIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 1. – С. 211-214.
100. Boltaeva M. J., Kh O. Ortikov. Features of the scientific heritage of eastern thinkers about the attitude of parents to the child //Society and innovations. Special. – 2021. – №. 2. – С. 469-474.